

Yield-attributing characters of rice as affected by Biozyme and NPK. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1993-94.

Treatment	Panicle length (cm)		Panicle weight (g)		Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		Spikelets m ⁻² ('000)		1,000-grain weight (g)	
	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
Control (no Biozyme and no NPK)	22.60	21.34	3.21	3.83	173.17	190.10	29.13	36.00	16.87	16.58
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer ^a	23.34	22.04	3.69	3.90	187.30	210.32	40.44	50.63	16.97	17.01
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	23.62	22.22	3.51	3.84	183.40	199.62	38.75	47.34	16.93	16.99
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	22.92	22.66	4.10	4.22	197.23	220.30	45.04	55.41	17.07	17.10
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	22.86	22.26	4.00	4.18	195.13	212.53	42.11	51.25	17.02	17.08
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	22.85	22.00	4.29	4.47	202.63	225.87	51.37	65.79	17.60	17.85
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	23.74	21.65	4.17	4.37	199.33	215.40	48.17	60.83	17.33	17.58
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	23.74	22.46	3.98	4.11	189.23	207.05	38.72	48.08	17.20	17.33
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	23.11	22.38	3.74	4.00	181.60	203.21	45.07	46.81	17.00	17.23
S _d ⁻	0.62	0.61	0.80	0.33	7.23	8.17	0.74	0.83	0.43	0.39
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	15.35	17.32	1.58	1.75	ns	ns
CV (%)	3.27	3.38	11.97	10.29	13.33	13.46	3.35	3.71	3.09	4.58

Treatment	Panicles m ² (no.)		Filled spikelets (%)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
Control (no Biozyme and no NPK)	175.31	200.11	81.12	84.34	2.1	2.2	3.8	4.2
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer ^a	227.33	255.73	82.67	86.83	2.9	3.2	4.8	6.0
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	218.44	249.42	81.57	86.18	2.8	3.2	4.6	5.8
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	243.62	261.15	85.03	87.17	3.3	3.5	5.4	6.4
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	231.23	255.80	83.19	86.99	3.2	3.4	5.3	6.2
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	265.19	309.43	85.96	89.96	3.5	3.7	5.2	7.0
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	258.92	297.37	85.49	88.89	3.4	3.6	5.6	6.6
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	218.65	247.13	84.96	86.93	3.0	3.3	5.0	5.1
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	264.91	245.56	84.08	86.77	2.9	3.3	5.0	5.9
S _d ⁻	18.85	21.22	3.35	3.21	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.5
LSD (0.05)	39.96	44.99	ns	ns	0.6	0.5	1.5	1.2
CV (%)	12.13	13.34	4.87	5.07	11.2	12.0	13.9	11.7

^a 120-60-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

Effects of fertilizer and green manure on survival and productivity of detached deepwater rice plants

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Deepwater rice plants sometimes get detached from the soil during the vegetative stage due to damage by crabs and other organisms. They then float in water. The survival of such plants depends on nodal roots that draw nutrients from the floodwater. Nodal roots can appear within 24 h

of stem detachment and improve the survival and productivity of deepwater rice.

Detached deepwater rice plants (128 d old) having only nodal roots were floated in concrete tanks containing 2400 liters of water. Treatments consisted of applying various fertilizers and "burying" of *Sesbania aculeata* plants in water (see table). The aim was to maintain a nutrient concentration of 5 or 10 ppm N in water.

Temperature and dissolved O₂ content of the water were measured at 6:20 a.m. and at 4:00 p.m. Average temperature was 29 °C in the morning and 31 °C in the afternoon. Water pH was measured at 9:00 a.m. and at 3:00 p.m. It increased by 0.5-1.0 unit in the

afternoon. After application of NP/NPK fertilizers, pH increased to within the 9.3-9.7 range due to algal growth. Decomposition of green manure lowered water pH, maintaining it between 7.2 and 8.2.

Dissolved O₂ concentration was generally higher in the afternoon than in the morning. In the presence of decomposing green manure, dissolved O₂ was 0.0-0.2 ppm in the morning and 1.0-6.6 ppm in the afternoon.

At crop maturity, four samples were harvested from each tank. There was a positive response to applied nutrients (see table). Application of NP gave NPK gave the best yields and were superior to application

Effect of fertilizers and green manure on yield of detached deepwater rice plants grown in water.

Treatment	Yield (g m ⁻² tank area)	
	Grain	Straw
No fertilizer (control)	14.4	261
5 ppm N as urea	25.1	321
10 ppm N as urea	27.4	329
5 ppm N through fresh <i>Sesbania aculeata</i> plants (3 kg)	22.6	326
5 ppm N as urea and 5 ppm P ₂ O ₅ as single superphosphate	37.5	394
5 ppm N as urea, 5 ppm P ₂ O ₅ as single superphosphate, and 5 ppm K ₂ O as muriate of potash	38.7	378
LSD (0.05)	6.9	39.5

of N alone, either through urea or green manure. The detached plants could complete their life cycle to grain filling and ripening without anchorage and nutrition from the soil. However, grain yield was low, with a maximum harvest index of 0.1. ■

Integrated N management with *Gliricidia maculata* and *Sesbania aculeata* for transplanted rice

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To save on fertilizer costs, green manure (GM) is used in conjunction with fertilizer N. We evaluated the effect of integrating GM *Gliricidia maculata* and *Sesbania aculeata* with different levels of fertilizer N (urea) on grain yield of transplanted rice in the 1989-90 rainy season. *Gliricidia* seedlings were planted on ricefield bunds at a distance of 0.5-1 m. The plants produced sufficient green loppings after 3 yr with 2.74% N, 0.5% P, and 1.1 % K in the leaves (dry weight basis). *Sesbania* was grown in situ at a seeding rate of 50 kg ha⁻¹ and incorporated in the soil after 45 d. *Sesbania* contained 2.9% N, 0.2% P, and 0.98% K. Soil was clay with pH 8.1, 0.6% organic C, and 200-42-346 kg available NPK ha⁻¹.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. GM crops were incorporated in the soil at transplanting. On the same day, 30-

Effect of green manure and fertilizer N on rice yield and comparative economic data. Maharashtra, India.

Treatment	Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Cost of cultivation (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Gross returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Net returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	B:C ^a
	1989	1990	Pooled mean				
100 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea in 3 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation (recommended)	3.6	2.6	3.1	344.99	404.71	59.72	1.17
5 t <i>G. maculata</i> ha ⁻¹ (27.4 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 50 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.1	2.2	2.6	330.10	342.95	12.85	1.04
7.5 t <i>G. maculata</i> ha ⁻¹ (41.1 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 25 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.4	2.5	2.9	334.80	385.00	50.20	1.15
5 t <i>S. aculeata</i> ha ⁻¹ (29 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 50 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.2	2.3	2.8	335.70	363.98	28.28	1.08
7.5 t <i>S. aculeata</i> ha ⁻¹ (43.5 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 25 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.4	2.1	2.7	333.35	357.41	24.06	1.07
Control (no N)	2.4	1.5	1.9	301.46	253.60	-47.86	0.84
SE±	0.2	0.2	0.1				
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.5	0.2				

^aBenefit-cost ratio.

to 35-d-old seedlings of 125-d-duration rice variety PLG1 were transplanted. P and K at 50 kg ha⁻¹ each were basally applied. N was applied as per treatment schedule (see table).

Fertilizer application at the recommended dose and integration of fertilizer N with GM proved superior to the control. Basal application of 7.5 t *G. maculata* with 25 kg urea N ha⁻¹ was on par with 100 kg urea N ha⁻¹ in terms of yield. Costs of cultivation, gross returns, net returns, and benefit-cost ratio of this integrated N management treatment were comparable with those of the recommended dose. With this treatment, a savings of 75 kg urea N ha⁻¹ may be achieved. ■

Fertilizer management— inorganic sources

Response of late-transplanted rice to NPK under irrigated conditions

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Rice followed by rapeseed - mustard is the most feasible double cropping system in Kashmir Valley (1650 m asl). But aberrant weather conditions (low temperature and cloudiness) delay transplanting. The NPK requirement of a crop under such a situation may differ from that of a timely planted rice crop, which usually requires 80-45-20 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

We conducted a 2-yr field trial at SKUAST's Shalimar Campus, on silty clay loam soil (pH 6.8, low available N and P, medium available K) during the 1990-91 wet seasons. The 18 treatments, tested in a randomized block design experiment with three replications, comprised different combinations of NPK levels (see table). Half the N and a full P and K dose were applied basally while the remaining N was applied in two splits: at tillering (18 d after transplanting [DAT]) and at panicle initiation (37 DAT).

Rice variety K39 was transplanted at 15 × 1.5-cm spacing at 3 seedlings per hill by the 1st week of Jul. During the experiment, temperatures ranged from 23.0 to 31.1 °C (maximum) and from 11.3 to 19.6 °C (minimum). Relative humidity was 45-76%. Total rainfall averaged 234 mm, spread over 35 d.